

Extraction of Traffic Flow Models Using Typical Traffic Information from Google

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Abstract

One way to control or reduce congestion is by sharing traffic information through traffic models. These models include the estimation of travel time from a desired place of origin-destination, the speed-flow-density parameters help to calculate the travel time. This thesis extracted traffic flow models by utilizing the extensive collection of real-time traffic information made available through Google Maps Application at a cost-efficient rate despite its representation of traffic conditions through color codes without the attachment of traffic models compared to the traditional methods of data collection to reduce traffic congestions. Therefore, the objective of this research includes data collection variables from Google Maps traffic information using real-time and historical traffic data, data processing by estimating vehicle speed, flow and density from Google traffic information through congestion color codes and model selection, development, and evaluation through the use of trendline equations. To create dynamic and precise traffic models, better understanding of traffic pattern is expected to lead to more efficient urban planning, traffic control, and infrastructure optimization.

Keywords: Traffic Flow Models, Google Maps

Introduction

Traffic congestion refers to the excessive number of vehicles on a road network, leading to a slow-down or halt in the flow of traffic. It occurs when the demand for road space exceeds its capacity to handle the volume of vehicles efficiently. It is a widespread issue in urban areas and can have significant effects on various aspects of life. According to [7], traffic congestion, especially in urban areas, has a major negative social and economic impact on society and the environment. Traffic congestion causes delays which significantly increases travel time for commuters leading to frustration and stress among drivers, passengers, and public transportation users affecting their productivity and overall well-being. Some significant economic impact includes increased fuel consumption, higher transportation cost for businesses, inefficiencies in the supply chain, and decreased productivity due to wasted time in traffic. Traffic congestion disrupts business activities and reduces productivity level, research has shown that it may also be a symbol of growth in an economy [31]. Congestion increases the likelihood of accidents, injuries, fatalities and road infrastructure degradation [3]. In addition to having a negative impact on public health, prolonged exposure to vehicle emissions can cause respiratory problems and other illnesses.

The livability of urban areas is affected by increased noise levels, diminishing the accessibility of public places, and creating barriers to social interactions. In industrialized nations, different measures are taken to reduce or control traffic congestion. Unfortunately, most cities in emerging nations are still in the experimental phase and will face traffic congestion [37]. Serious traffic congestion on urban roads is caused by the economy's rapid development, a sharp rise in the number of cars on the roads, and inadequate building of urban infrastructure. The main problem facing developing economies, according to [24], is the ongoing growth in traffic congestion brought on by a rise in car ownership. Several solutions can be implemented to address traffic congestion, such as improved public transportation by enhancing and expanding public transportation networks which can provide viable alternatives to private vehicles. Traffic management and regulations help improve traffic flow and reduce congestion by implementation of effective traffic management strategies such as signal coordination, lane management and congestion pricing. Telecommuting and flexible work hours also help distribute traffic demand throughout the day, reducing peak-hour congestion. The development of infrastructure such as building new roads, highways, and bridges can help alleviate congestion. Carpooling and ride-sharing are

facilitate additional ways to reduce the number of cars on the road. Ride-hailing services and carpooling apps cost-sharing and decrease congestion by promoting shared rides.

A nation's transportation system is one of the resources required for its economic, social, and physical security. The ability of a transportation system to move people and commodities from one place to another in a safe, useful, and economical way determines how important that system is. The gathering of traffic data for traffic management, traffic control, trend monitoring, economic research, and traffic planning is known as traffic studies and analysis. According to [27], studies on traffic engineering and transportation typically fall into one of four categories: (1) physical inventories, such as roadway characteristics and conditions, control devices, and parking spaces; (2) population characteristics, such as road-user and vehicle-population data; (3) measurement of operational parameters, such as volume, speed, and density; and (4) special studies such as accident and parking studies, and trip generation/traffic impact studies. In order to move people and goods safely and quickly, traffic flow, which is closely tied to traffic characteristics, is required. Different aspects of the daily observed traffic flow can be seen depending on the time of day, they are brought on by traffic incidents including collisions, broken-down vehicles, construction work, and other odd occurrences.

The movement of individual cars and their interactions with one another between two locations is the subject of traffic flow analysis. Traffic state can be classified into three; low, medium, and high flow conditions. The volume, speed, and density of a traffic flow are its three main determinants. Since the early half of the 20th century, traffic flow has been researched. Because of its numerous applications in transportation, the field of study is expanding. Congestion and traffic flow in the transportation sector are two of the major societal and economic issues in developed nations. In connection with this, managing traffic in congested networks necessitates a clear grasp of traffic flow operations, i.e., knowledge of the factors that influence the timing and location of traffic breakdowns, the way that congestion spreads throughout the network, etc.

The vehicle flow is a vehicle composition interacting with one another, and their operational attribute can be described mathematically [9]. If users can obtain timely, accurate, and trustworthy traffic information, then some demand has to be minimized, rerouted, or relocated to other days [8]. Traffic flow models are computational models that aim to describe and predict vehicular movement on road networks. These models are used to analyze traffic patterns, optimize traffic control strategies for efficiency and safety, and design transportation infrastructure. The development of a traffic flow model is one of the important solutions for traffic congestion which help in the efficient movement of the traffic. Movement of vehicles are described in terms of variables such as speed, density, and flow rate. Traffic models help in efficient movement of traffic flow which helps in the reduction of traffic congestion.

High quality real-time traffic information is essential for the development of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS). Over the past few years, as the need for better traffic management has grown, methods for gathering traffic data have changed significantly, and access to real-time traffic data is now commonplace across the globe [19]. For applications in location-based services (LBS), intelligent transportation systems (ITS), advanced traveler information systems (ATIS), and public transit systems, real-time transit service data that considers accessibility measurement can provide vital information about the efficacy and quality of the service [26],[24]. As a result, OpenStreetMap (OSM) and Google Maps have emerged as online mapping tools to support decision-making in transportation operations [33],[34].

A data-driven pipeline using online map vendors was proposed by [38] as the data source for urban-scale traffic modeling which showed that the similarity of road segments can be determined by their traffic flow patterns rather than their spatial and geometric properties. This metric of similarity applies to road segments not only from the same city, but also from different cities, thus revealing a new layer of information for urban planning and urban management. The criticism of Greenshields' 1934 experiments, which established a linear relationship between the flow, speed, and density of cars in the traffic stream on the highway, gave rise to all traffic models. Through constructive critique, researchers like Greenberg, North-western, Underwood, Edie, Lighthill, and Whitham have all been building on the research sparked by Greenshields to increase the efficacy of each model as it is put forth.

The analysis, prediction, and optimization of vehicular movement on roads and highways are made possible by traffic flow models and theories, which are essential tools for transportation engineering. Three major categories of traffic models have reportedly been found, including macroscopic, mesoscopic, and microscopic models [32]. For a successful traffic flow model to be built, data collection is a necessity. Trip duration is a crucial network performance metric for road system operators, although road users are free to choose and plan their own route [28]. The need for traffic modeling can be seen in its reliability in predicting the changes in traffic behavior and demonstrating the traffic status under different road network conditions. For example, the modeling characteristics of some traffic related

problems, such as traffic congestion, travel delays and traffic accidents, will provide a description of the traffic status to help traffic management to control these traffic problems. Traffic operations on roadways can be improved by field research and field experiments of real-life traffic flow. However, apart from the scientific problem of reproducing such experiments, costs and safety play a role of dominant importance as well.

Recent transportation research has mainly aimed to address the aforementioned issues by controlling traffic congestion and reducing the amount of time that traffic is congested. In order to estimate and anticipate the traffic pattern, researchers in developed nations fund intelligent transportation research [35]. To do this, they collect traffic data using loop detectors, RFID, and sensor networks. Because they are prohibitively expensive for developing countries, require specialized equipment for their installation and maintenance, necessitate experienced personnel visiting locations, and cause traffic disruptions, data collected through these traditional processes are constrained in terms of their coverage [36].

According to [17], there are a number of reasons why traffic congestion has developed in some locations. This growing bottleneck is posing a threat to large metropolitan centers. Several studies used GPS tracing or sensors placed at various crossings to gather traffic data [15],[29],[39],[1].

According to research, traffic status predictions made from historical sensor-based data may be less accurate. For this reason, the CTM-EKF-GA framework which was developed without the use of historical traffic data was presented by Ahmed and his colleagues. As an alternative, they collected at a from what are referred to as connected cars, or CVs, that collect real-time traffic data [4]. Some research studies have attempted collecting traffic information from a number of developing nations such as India, Pakistan, Myanmar and Bangladesh through manual counts but had limitations such as erroneous counting, time consuming, non-scalable and cumbersome manual counting.[30]collected data with manual count using an interval of fifteen-minutes and duration of four-hours for a case study area for the optimization of signal timing.[18]collected data through manual count at a duration of one-hour for VISSIM simulation.

Manual counting was used in India during two peak hours of the working day, high-quality digital cameras were installed on cars and placed across a few two- and four-lane highways from three intersections, machine learning models were used to forecast traffic congestion [6]. This short-term traffic forecast only covered a tiny section of the highway. Several researchers used GPS to gather traffic data for various analyses.[20] collected data using GPS from several taxis for 11769 road segments for the study of traffic patterns which was limited in such a way that data collected were not usable for traffic intensity prediction. In order to anticipate traffic intensity,[10] gathered GPS data from a Bangladesh telecommunications provider using cars equipped with GPS monitoring devices. However, this traffic information was taken at an hourly interval, the number of vehicles were restricted, and the interval was too high to accurately estimate traffic patterns. For traffic congestion prediction, GPS data was collected [14], by tracking mobile phones on a few designated automobiles in Yangon, Myanmar data was gathered including traffic speed, direction, timestamps, and other GPS data in order to estimate the congestion based on customer demand. Although, large scale data collection could not be performed as focus was only on android phones.

In summary, the cited traditional data collection processes have been identified with limitations such as expensive deployment of sensors and loop detectors, non-feasible data collection using GPS from representative number of motorized vehicles, manual counting requires a lot of human labor and equipment since it is a laborious, time-consuming, and non-scalable process. However, for massive collecting scenarios involving traffic for an entire city, the methodologies are not scalable.

An online resource that provides extensive information about places and regions worldwide is Google Maps. A great way to find best route to a location. Traffic views and faster-route suggestions on Google Maps are based on two types of data: real-time data from sensors and smartphones that report the speed at which cars are moving at any given moment, and historical data about the average time it takes to travel a specific section of road at specific times on specific days. The Google application integrates position information from participants' smartphones with GPS with data from a conventional sensor [12].

One of the many aspects of the performance of the transportation system that contributes to more sensible investment choices for transportation enhancement is the monitoring of congestion. Traffic data must be gathered in developing nations in a scalable, customizable and economically viable way. In the past, the expensive infrastructure of cameras and sensors was used to collect traffic data. Thus, data collection should focus on the most crucial locations rather than the entire transportation network. Because of this, certain programs that gather data more quickly and effectively have been created.

The segment's length, the number of intersections along the way, traffic density, speed, and flow are all taken into account while calculating travel time. The key variables in traffic engineering are traffic flow, speed, and density [11]. According to [5], this data aids in the identification of various traffic conditions (such as free-flow, congested, etc.) and events (such as joining or leaving a line of traffic, the propagation of shockwaves, etc.). Using real and recent data from the Google Maps API,[2] proposed an approach to estimate the speeds within defined geographical areas (i.e zip codes) per daytime and per weekday to classify and define different urban-congestion levels according to estimated speeds, number of inhabitants, zone types and the type of roads in each zip code by using k-means clustering as part of statistical analysis. Access to current and reliable geographic data as well as spatial analysis tools for comprehending patterns of urban mobility was made possible via the Google API.

Google uses four different colors to encode the numerical data and distributes it for free via its online and mobile app platforms. Where there is no traffic delay indicated by the color green. Medium traffic is represented by the color orange, and traffic delays are represented by the color red. The color dark red stands for slower moving traffic on the route. According to [13], the gray tint denotes a lack of readings in the passing automobiles. In numerous cities throughout the world, this color-coded traffic (live and usual) is accessible. Data from more than a billion users who are active each month are pooled to produce Google traffic statistics [21]. By default, the user allows Google's location service to disclose their location information, which is then processed further in the Google database. It is unknown even with the increase in smartphone usage, if color-coded traffic signals remain dependable in emerging countries, Internet connectivity, and Google active users.

By preventing users' identities from being revealed, Google has protected users' privacy and encouraged them to keep this option enabled. Google shows the current traffic situation in a certain location using a lot of data from active mobile phones [25].

[16] assumed a method to facilitate data acquisition and delay in a fast and cost-effective manner which was done through the use of websites on the Internet, one of which is Google traffic maps. It worked towards providing data on the traffic situation of the roads in any area, and at any time in the world, which can be used to know the amount of delay of the trip in these areas. This method was adopted due to cost efficiency, effectiveness, and time. In order to acquire traffic data for any road segments or intersections smoothly from any place in a city,[22] proposed a novel approach to collect traffic data from Google Map's traffic layer using its paid API at a minimal cost before the implementation of widely used models such as historical averages (HA), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Support Vector Regression with Graph (SVR-Graph), and Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) to show the efficacy of collected traffic data in forecasting future congestion. This strategy was observed to be scalable from a small area to the full metropolis.

[23] developed a tool that collects traffic data from Google Maps without using its paid API. Likewise, an Attention-based Deep Hybrid Network (ADHN) was proposed for traffic flow prediction using Google map data. The proposed ADHN combines two Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory (ConvLSTM) to capture dynamic spatial temporal dependencies of the traffic flow and applies attention mechanism on traffic features. The experiment result showed that the proposed ADHN can provide higher prediction accuracy compared with the other state-of-the-art approaches.

[36] developed a traffic congestion model that uses calibrated equations for density/flow and speed/density for many Google traffic indicators, based on traffic data from Ecuador. Despite certain limitations, such as data acquired from a single city with a potentially different urban environment than others, for the benefit of street designers and urban planners, this study provides insight on the application of Google traffic indicators in metropolitan areas.

The aim of this research is to conduct a validation of the traffic flow models used by Google Maps a cost- efficient tool, comparing their performance against established expensive traffic flow models. The validation process will involve real-world data collection and comparison of results, ensuring that Google Maps-based models are accurate and reliable enough for transportation planning and management applications. This study will use ground truth data and data from Google Maps to calibrate equations for Google's color-coded indicators of traffic congestion.

Materials and Method

Data Sources

A fundamental aspect of the data collection process is comprehending the data's sources. The main data source for this study was Google Maps, a popular tool for traffic monitoring and navigation. Google Maps is an indispensable tool for traffic flow analysis since it offers a plethora of information, including historical traffic statistics, real-time traffic updates, as well as extensive geographic data.

Data Acquisition

Ground truth data and Google traffic information were the two sets of variables that were gathered. First, the traffic color code was taken from Google applications (web or mobile). There are four available colors: green indicates no traffic delays, orange indicates a medium level of traffic, red indicates delays in traffic, and darker red indicates slower traffic on the route. Vehicle speeds and traffic volume were recorded in the ground truth data.

Data was recorded for 6 November 2023 and 10 November 2023 through manual collecting of color code during the hours of (08h00 to 18h00). This time frame was chosen because that is when Google typically reports traffic figures for the research area.

Vehicle speeds and traffic movement were manually recorded. With the vehicles gathered, the flow of traffic was approximated for a 15-minute period. Two pavement markers spaced 25 meters apart were used to estimate the vehicle's speed, along with the amount of time it took the vehicle to pass the marks. Speeds of vehicles were calculated using data that was true to ground truth. Every 15 minutes, it determined the average speed and flow of traffic. The computed speed and flow were used to determine density. The congestion color-codes were related to those parameters.

Traffic Flow Model Development

To accurately depict traffic situations for creating traffic flow models, real-time traffic data analysis was conducted by retrieving real-time data through the continuous access and retrieval of real-time traffic data via Google Maps application. This real-time data is vital for understanding current traffic situations.

Study Area

Minna is the capital of Niger State of Nigeria with roughly 496,000 inhabitants. The study area (Kpakungu) is located in the Chanchaga LGA which is an urban center in the North central that lies between latitude 9°37' to 9°39' North and longitude 6°30' to 6°33' East. The issue of transportation and traffic is very concerning. The rapid rise in diverse vehicle traffic and the availability of inadequate transportation infrastructure facilities, along with the expanding population, have become major contributors to these issues. The study area links numerous locations around the city, including commercial, residential, industrial, religious, institutional, and recreational spaces, therefore making them suitable for in-depth analysis and the development of traffic flow models. The selected area represents diverse traffic scenarios, including urban, suburban, and peri-urban contexts, enabling to study a broad spectrum of traffic flow dynamics. Accessing a substantial amount of historical and real-time traffic data for the area via Google Maps plays a significant role.

Figure 1. Kpakungu axis

Model Calibration and Validation

The process of evaluating the calibrated traffic flow model's accuracy and dependability is known as model validation. It is a critical step to ensure that the model can effectively replicate real-world

traffic conditions. Comparison of the model's predictions to actual traffic data from the selected study area was carried out. This comparison involved evaluating model-predicted flow rates, speeds, and densities against observed values.

Results

Calibration and Validation of Equations

Despite the representation of traffic conditions through color codes without the attachment of traffic models by Google Maps comparison was done with the traditional methods of data collection to reduce traffic congestions. Speed behavior patterns were examined using bar charts by plotting ground truth speeds against the congestion color codes as shown below.

Figure 2. Graph of average ground truth speed by several traffic indicators from Google. NTD: no traffic delay, MLT: medium level of traffic, DT: delay in traffic, STR: slower traffic on route.

The speed drops from "no traffic delay" (green color) to "slower traffic on route" (darker red), as seen in figure 2. Though there is a large range of speeds in the plotted graph, the same speed can be found in another plotted graph for different traffic situations. For example, 13 km/hr is found in green color (no traffic delay), and orange color (medium level of traffic). The relationships between flow, density, and speed were analyzed using the color-coded indicators.

Figure 3. Relationship between Flow and Density by several traffic indicators from Google

The plot in the figure above shows the relationship between flow and density on the Kpakungu axis by several traffic indicators from Google. Furthermore, trend lines were drawn in the graph above so that various R-squared values could be compared to one another. The density-flow relationship curve frequently takes the form of an inverted U. Only a portion of the curve is covered by the data in these situations. Density increases along with flow until an inflection point is reached, at which point flow starts to decrease but density keeps rising. The trends in the figure do not approach the point of inflection. Interestingly, the data slope flattens with increasing congestion (NTD, MLT, TD, and STR). Table 1 shows the various equation.

Figure 4. Relationship between Speed and Density by several traffic indicators from Google

The above graph shows the relationship between speed and density on the Kpakungu axis by several traffic indicators from Google. Trend lines from the figure were used to compare R-squared values to other trend lines. According to the fundamental diagram theory of the speed-density relationship a linear trend is expected. The data trends are inconsistent with the fundamental diagram having different R-squared values from trend line. Table 1 shows the various equation.

Figure 5. Relationship between Speed and Flow by several traffic indicators from Google.

The plot in the figure above shows the relationship between speed and flow on the Kpakungu axis by several traffic indicators from Google. Trend lines were plotted to compare various R-squared values. Table 1 shows the equations.

Table 1. Calibrated equations for speed/flow, speed/density and density/flow for several Google traffic indicators

Traffic indicator	Color code	Calibrated equation	Trendline	R ² value	S/N
NTD	Green	$u=0.0167q^2-2.4842q+103.03$	Polynomial	0.5577	(1)
		$u= 35.68k^{0.585}$	Power	0.9391	(2)
		$q=27.337e^{0.215k}$	Exponential	0.7831	(3)
MLT	Orange	$u=2.2593\ln(q)+ 3.7304$	Logarithmic	0.2023	(4)
		$u=-0.1601k^2+ 1.0681k+10.532$	Polynomial	0.0511	(5)
		$q=26.043\ln(k)+14.66$	Logarithmic	0.6953	(6)
DT	Red	$u=0.0008q^2-0.0504q+4.4161$	Polynomial	0.027	(7)
		$u=0.0743k^2-0.9632k+5.5143$	Polynomial	0.2732	(8)
		$q=3.9341e^{0.2203k}$	Exponential	0.9718	(9)
STR	Dark red	$u=-0.0113q^2+ 0.3057q + 0.8239$	Polynomial	0.3163	(10)
		$u=-0.0157k^2+ 0.1996k+1.8146$	Polynomial	0.0818	(11)
		$q=-0.1808k^2+ 4.2829k-4.064$	Polynomial	0.7879	(12)

In the table above, u= average speed (km/hr), q= traffic flow (veh./hr), k= traffic density (veh./km), NTD: no traffic delay, MLT: medium level of traffic, DT: delay in traffic, STR: slower traffic on route.

From Table 1 it is observed that low R-squared values were obtained at MLT of 0.0511 and 0.2023, DT of 0.2732 and 0.027, and STR of 0.0818 and 0.3163 for the speed-density and speed-flow relationship respectively due to limited traffic data collection.

Conclusion

The study aimed to strike a balance between reducing the cost of data collection while ensuring the accuracy of the data collected for traffic flow modeling.

Several key findings and achievements have emerged from this research such as: Data collection efficiency by openly available traffic data from Google Maps, effective reduction in the cost of data collection. Access to real-time traffic data has been established without the need for extensive sensor

deployments or expensive data acquisition methods. The model calibration and validation process for traffic flow models have been fine-tuned to replicate real-world conditions through the use of trendline equations producing various R-squared values for speed-flow, speed-density and density-flow to represent the different traffic conditions identified by Google Maps through the different color codes.

This study has a limitation of less traffic data collection that led to an unclear relationship between the ground truth data and Google traffic indicators. Therefore, to acquire a clear relationship for accuracy and reliability more traffic data needs to be collected for a better validation of traffic flow models used by Google Maps. Data quality assurance needs to be taken into consideration thereby strict processes should be followed while preprocessing data to ensure data quality. To cut down on errors and inconsistencies in the collected data, numerous traffic data, extensive data cleansing, anomaly detection, and validation testing are required.

By adhering to the recommendation, the study can achieve a balance between cost-effective data collection and the accuracy of traffic flow parameter estimation. It can also contribute to more efficient traffic management and transportation planning in urban areas, ultimately leading to improved traffic conditions and enhanced urban mobility.

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